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EFFECT OF GLAZIGLANG (DISTANCE BETWEEN GLASSES) IN ANIMAL FEED COOKER

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ABSTRACT

The animal feed cooker is constructed in the rural area by available material in the area like animal dung, sand, soil bricks etc. The structure which is made by these materials is not works for a long time and maintenance cost of the structure is also high. These structures are made to reduce the cost of the construction of animal feed cooker. To reduce maintenance cost and economic construction of solar animal feed cooker an animal feed cooker is made which is constructed by the bricks, sand, cement, aggregates. The strength of the animal feed cooker is high and maintenance cost is also low. The concrete animal feed cooker can be used for a long time than the previous cookers. The animal feed cookers reduce cooking time of animal feed and save wood, animal dung, leaves and the natural fuel. The temperature of structure is reach at the time of cooking about 80c to 100c.

INTRODUCTION :-

In cooking of the animal feed wood, animal dung (cow, buffalo), natural fuel is used. To reduce and save the natural traditional fuel which is used as fertilizers in agricultural farms in the rural areas solar animal feed cooker is used.

Firewood is used in cooking of animal feed cooker which is received from the forests, farms etc. It is harmful for environment and cause of global warming. The fertilizers which are useful in farming are used in cooking of animal feed. It is costly and uneconomical for farmers. The burning amount of agricultural waste, fertilizers, animal dung can be used in agriculture farms.

SUN INTENSITY:- P. Sharma and N. M. Nahar, G. R. Choudhary has described that:-

The desert area shows 7200-7800 MJm⁻² per year which is maximum radiation intensity in India. and minimum radiation intensity shows at mountainous area 6200 MJm⁻² per year.

The maximum radiation intensity recorded is 1500 w/m² and maximum temperature is about 35 c to 50 c. in summer season.

It is very important and suitable conditions for animal feed cooker in India.

1. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:-

First of all George Louis Leclere Buffon (1707-1788) made the solar stove but Nicholasde-Saussure (1740-1799) use solar energy for cooking. Adams was made first solar cooker (1878) in India and cooked food in Mumbai, who was an army officer. Presently solar cookers are made by animal dung, clay, pearl millet husk etc. by Central Arid Zone, Research Institute Jodhpur (CAZRI).

2. STRUCTURE:-

In structure of animal feed cooker two same size chambers are made which are 2'x 2'x 5" in size. This structure is constructed by sand, cement, bricks and aggregates. Cement polish is used to finishing. The blocks are divided by a middle wall.

Wooden frames are used to cover the blocks which are made of sagwan. Two couple glasses frames are used for every block and spacing between the glasses are kept 20 mm and 30 mm. Sagwan is used to reduce heat loss due to cover and black board color is used to paint the surface of the blocks. Black board color is used to absorb heat by sun. Rubber is used to block the gaps in the frame which increase the heat of the solar cooker.

SOLAR COOKER FOR ANIMAL FEED

4.PROCESS:-

In boiling of animal feed. Crushed barley (Jau Ghat), guar korma, and gram churi with water are kept in pans (tagari) . And cover the tagari to decrease the time of cooking. And wooden frame are tightly closed and sunlight are passed through the glass and pressure is developed inside the chamber And animal feed is cooked by this process. And we are testing at different temperature, different quantities and different spacing of glass in both the chambers. And also test cover and non-cover material condition. Measure the temperature with hydrometer and thermometer at outside or inside the chamber.

Cook animal feed in both the chambers simultaneously. And check which method is suitable for cooking of animal feed and the process is fast in which method. And In present we construct the structure and the test are in progress.

5.TABLES OF READING:-

Temperature (Without Material (Empty)) Degree Celsius

Time	Block I (10 mm Spacing)		Block II (20 mm Spacing)		Environment Temp.
	Outer	Inner	Outer	Inner	
12:30 PM	40	65	56	89	40
01:30 PM	46	71	65	101	42
02:30 PM	41	70	58	100	40
03:30 PM	50	66	60	89	38

Temperature (With Material) Degree Celsius

Time	Block I (10 mm spacing)		Block II (20 mm Spacing)		Environment Temp.
	Outer	Inner	Outer	Inner	
10:00 AM	39	30	30	42	31
11:00 AM	45	39	33	59	32
12:00 PM	52	48	39	72	35
01:00 PM	55	54	41	80	36
02:00 PM	45	57	50	90	38
03:00 PM	43	55	60	86	36

Temperature (With Material) Degree Celsius

Time	Block I (10mm Spacing) With Cover (Closed)		Block II (20mm Spacing) Without Cover(Open)		Environment Temperature
	Outer	Inner	Outer	Inner	
10:00 AM	42	30	32	35	31
11:00 AM	62	36	38	50	33
12:00 PM	61	40	39	57	32
01:00 PM	57	46	38	59	35
02:00 PM	62	41	42	58	37
03:00 PM	68	43	43	62	36
04:00 PM	52	45	38	57	36

Note – All Reading are in Degree Celsius.

Material :-3 kg in every block.

Guar, Fenugreek , and cotton seed are mixed in equal proportion 1 kg each. Water ratio is 1:8

6. METHOD:-

SPACING BETWEEN GLASSES (GLAZING):-

- In the process we used a wood frame which is set twice couple of glasses at different Distance.
- Distance between two glasses of 1 block is 10mm.
- Distance between 2 block glasses is 20mm.
- Spacing between the glasses is kept by the small wooden sticks.
- Size and thickness of the glasses are same in the frames.
- Total four glasses are used in the cooker.

EFFECT OF GLAZING:-

In reading results shows that the 20mm spacing block is occurs higher temperature than 10mm spacing block. It is shows that increasing distance between glasses is increase heat in the block and it is good for animal feed cooking and reduces time of feed cooking. But there is a limit in increasing distance between the glasses to increase heat of the chamber.

7. CONCLUSION:-

Animal feed cooker is economical in rural areas and ecofriendly to save firewood and fertilizers. Total cost of an animal is about 6500rs. A perfect spacing between the glasses reduces cooking time of animal feed and saves fertilizers like animal dung, leaves, farm waste etc.

The trees can be saved by the animal feed cooker by saving firewood.

- Cost: - 6500rs
- Material: - cement, sand, bricks, aggregates
- Life: - 10-15 years
- Capacity: - 8-10 kg per day

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